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Loss of CCR4 silencing in the blood correlates with active disease in humans with Crohn's Disease.

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Chemokine receptors control local and tissue-specific immune activation by guiding recruitment of immune cells through gradient expression. We describe here loss of silencing of CCR4, the receptor for chemokines CCL2, CCL4, CCL5, CCL17, and CCL22, in the whole blood in humans with Crohn's Disease. CCR4 derepression was associated with disease activity in humans with Crohn's Disease.